

franchisees. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 33(4), 22–33.

9. Shane, S. (1996). Hybrid organizational arrangements and their implications for firm growth and survival: A study of new franchisors. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39(1), 216-234.

10. Elango, B., & Fried, V.H. (1997). Franchising research: a literature review and synthesis. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 35(3), 68-81.

11. Smith, G.R. (1998). Franchising and licensing: Two powerful ways to grow your business in any economy. New York: John Wiley & Sons.

12. Altinay, L., & Brookes, M. (2012). Factors influencing the growth of franchise systems: An international study. *Journal of Marketing Channels*, 19(4), 259-278.

13. Eroglu, S., & Machleit, K.A. (1990). An empirical study of retail crowding: Antecedents and consequences. *Journal of Retailing*, 66(2), 201-221.

14. Barkema, H.G., & Vermeulen, F. (1998). International expansion through start-up or acquisition: A learning perspective. *Academy of Management Journal*, 41(1), 7-26.

15. Manolis, C., Dahlstrom, R., & Nygaard, A. (1995). A preliminary investigation of ownership conversions and strategic change. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 11(1), 1-7.

16. Terry, A., & DiLernia, A. (2008). Franchising in the medical laboratory sector: assessing the potential for a new business model. *Health Marketing Quarterly*, 25(1-2), 53-70.

17. Perrigot, R., & Cliquet, G. (2008). The plural form in service chain networks: The case of the French laboratory sector. *The Service Industries Journal*, 28(2), 273-288.

18. Hoy, F., & Shane, S. (1998). Franchising as an entrepreneurial venture form. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 13(2), 91-94.

19. Hackett, D.W., & Srinivasan, R. (1998). The role of pre-entry experience, entry timing, and market strategy in the performance of new franchise systems. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 13(4), 253-273.

20. Justis, R.T., & Judd, R.J. (1998). Franchising. Cincinnati: South-Western College Publishing.

21. Preble, J.F. (1999). The influence of service franchising on organizational learning. *The Learning Organization*, 6(1), 18-28.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PIN STRUCTURES USED IN THE RESTORATION OF THE CROWN PART OF THE TEETH

İsmaylov D.,

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry*

Demirchiyeva M.,

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry*

Kerimli N.

*Department of Therapeutic c Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7944962>

Abstract

A clinical assessment of the quality of restoration of the crowns of pulpless teeth using various pin designs was made. In the course of clinical studies, the main pin structures used to restore destroyed tooth crowns were analyzed.

Keywords: pins, pulpless teeth, restoration.

Restoration of crowns of teeth, especially depulped ones, is an urgent problem in dentistry [1]. To restore the structure and function of such teeth, it is very important to choose the correct pin design [2]. It is thanks to the use of reinforcing elements that the restored tooth will be able to fully perform its function [3]. Based on the data of a clinical study, a dentist must choose a design from a large number of various pins that would fully correspond to the clinical situation [4].

The purpose of the study was to clinically evaluate the quality of restoration of crowns of pulpless teeth using different pin designs.

Materials and methods

We have analyzed the main pin structures used to restore destroyed tooth crowns. Patients with defects in

the crowns of the teeth underwent restoration of teeth with MOOSER pins ("Maillefer") - 3 patients,

UNIMETRIC ("Maillefer") - 5 patients, RADIXANKER ("Maillefer") - 3 patients, CYTCO ("Maillefer") - 3 patients, FLEXI-POST (SDS) - 5 patients; and with the help of a cast pin tab with individual modeling - 5 patients. In all cases, glass ionomer cement was used to fix the pins, and the crown part was restored using a composite material. Immediately after filling, the quality of the restoration of the tooth surface at the border between the root and the filling material and the contact point using flosses were checked. The introduction of floss into the interdental space should be difficult, but it should move freely on the surface of

the tooth and filling. If the floss loses its structure (separates into individual fibers), this indicates a poor-quality surface restoration. After 6 months, in addition to floss control, the condition of the interdental papilla and filling was determined. In the presence of inflammation of the papilla, an X-ray of the filled tooth was performed.

The choice of post type largely depends on the volume of the root canal after endodontic treatment, as well as on the loss of dentinal mass of the crown or tooth root [5]. Most dentists believe that when restoring a tooth after endodontic treatment, it must be strengthened with pins, regardless of the degree of tooth decay [5,6]. The pins must have the following characteristics:

- provide a long term endodontic obturation;
- correspond to the canal anatomy;
- take into account the resistance of the tooth root;
- provide reliable coronal retention of obturation;
- do not disturb the structure of dentin;
- to ensure the restoration of the crown-root part in the simplest way;
- to maintain the tightness of endodontic treatment by cementing the post.

It is difficult to determine what should be the ideal post that can be used in all clinical cases. Such a pin must meet the basic requirements:

- have a cylindrically conical shape with the possibility of modeling the coronal part and good retention;
- be made of titanium, carbon, precious or semi-precious alloys;
- have different sizes;
- must not self-block in the channel.

Each tooth, depending on its position in the dentition, has its own occlusal load acts in different directions. With a vertical load and the parallelism of the side walls of the pin, there is a slight pressure on the walls of the channel. With regard to horizontal loading, it is better to use a cast post with a round section, anatomically adapted to the structure of the root canal. Fixation of the pin should be at the level of half or two-thirds of the root canal. The ideal pin diameter is determined by the 1/3 rule (equal to one third of the mesiodistal diameter of the root in which the pin is inserted) [3]. Roll pins are the easiest to use and have good retention, but their shape does not match the shape of the tooth, so the risk of perforation is high. They are usually used in short and massive roots. With tapered pins, retention decreases as the taper angle increases. They are more adapted morphologically, and the pressure at the level of the root apex is insignificant. They are strong, but due to their shape they cause a feeling of wedging [7]. The surface of the pin can be smooth, corrugated, have a screw cut or be combined. Smooth pins include MOOSER pins ("Maillefer"). They have a screw groove, thanks to which the material can be obtained with

fixation. Pin heads are flattened. Each pin diameter corresponds to a conical bur.

UNIMETRIC screw pins (Maillefer) have square heads with retention grooves. Available in 2 diameters: 0.8 mm with short and long heads.

Combined pins RADIX-ANKER ("Maillefer") - the part of the pin under the head has a screw thread,

and the lower part is smooth, the apical tip has a rounded shape. CYTCO pins ("Maillefer") are conical in their apical part and cylindrical in

cervical part. The first third of the cylindrical part has a retention thread for self-screwing, while the conical part of the pin no longer has it.

It has. This type of post anchors well in teeth with strong root walls, reducing the risk of fracture. The post head is made in such a way that it provides good retention of the restorative material. Its base is located horizontally at the level of the root and provides a solid support. The conical part without screw thread is located at the level of the root apex, repeating its anatomy and not leading to a decrease in wall thickness. Two longitudinal grooves ensure the exit of cement residues during fixation.

FLEXI-POST Screw Posts (SDS) are titanium posts with a long and thick retention head. They are screw-threaded and self-screw, forming their own thread in the dentin. The collars are precisely adapted to the center of the calibration hole. This design provides the correct lateral load along the entire length of the channel, and the longitudinal slots reduce the risk of overpressure during twisting and ensure the release of cementing material residues. This system has the best retention. The length of the pins is adjusted by grinding or sharpening. For photoelasticity data, FLEXI-POST posts optimally distribute the load (maximum reduction of root stress), and SCREW-POSTS cylindrical posts have the most unfavorable properties.

A feature of the preparation of the tooth root for pins is the formation of a seat and threading on the canal wall. When expanding and forming a seat, it is necessary to work at low speeds of the drill with mandatory cooling, without excessive pressure on the reamer or cutter. The diameter of the cutter must be less than the diameter of the channel, so that the thickness of the walls of the channel on all sides after milling is at least 1.5 mm, and the depth of the seat is 2 mm. This must be observed so as not to weaken the root walls. The cut in the channel is created using a calibration tap with slight pressure. After 1-2 turns, it is unscrewed and cleaned of dentin residues. The length of the thread should be 1-3 mm longer than on the pin. The root canal is washed, dried, filled with cement and the pin is screwed in. After tightening, turn the pin counterclockwise by 0.25-0.5 turns to reduce internal stress. After complete hardening, the crown part of the tooth is formed using restorative materials.

It should be noted that the design of standard pins with an artificial stump is used to restore single-rooted teeth, provided that it is not necessary to change the slope of the cult part of the design. If it needs to be changed (in case of an abnormal position or inclination of the teeth), the usual design of a cast pin tab with individual modeling should be used. It is not optimal in use because it does not provide shock absorption of the horizontal

occlusal load component. At the top of the pin, a significant load is concentrated, equal to 250% of the external chewing load, which can lead to tooth decay.

Reduces these disadvantages of the design, which has a "grinder" of the horizontal component of the functional load. In this case, a stress equal to only 80% of the external load is concentrated at the top of the pin. The optimal angle should be 40-50 degrees relative to the axis of the tooth.

An analysis of the immediate results of the study showed that during the restoration of teeth with pins MOOSER ("Maillefer"), in 2 cases, decementation of the structure occurred. The reason, in our opinion, is the weak retention of glass ionomer cement to a smooth post.

When using pins UNIMETRIC ("Maillefer") in 1 case there was a depressurization in the gingival part from the palatal side. The reason, perhaps, was the overload of the restored tooth, because the patient had no chewing teeth on one side.

There were no such complications in the group that used RADIXANKER (Maillefer) screw-threaded posts. But in one case, a root crack was found in the gingival area of the tooth, which may have been formed due to the pressure of the material during screwing. There were no complications when using FLEXI-POST (SDS) pins. But it must be taken into account that pins of this type were fixed at the root, which had stronger walls. The design of the molded pin insert with individual modeling was used when changing the inclination tooth. The main disadvantage in this case was the chips of the filling material, which was used to restore the crown. Therefore, all restorations were changed to metal-ceramic crowns.

Therefore, different pin designs can be used to restore decayed teeth, but in our experience, the most optimal is the use of FLEXI-POST (SDS) screw posts.

It is titanium pins with a long and thick retention head that provide the correct lateral load along the entire length of the canal, and longitudinal slots reduce the risk of increased pressure during twisting and ensure the release of cementing material residues. This system has the best retention.

References:

1. Morgano S.M. Restavracija depul'pirpovannyh zubov: primenenie obychnyh principov v real'nyh i budushhih kontekstah / S.M. Morgano. - M.: Vysshaja shkola, 1990. – S. 3-23.
2. Sravnenie biomehaniki shtiftovyh konstrukcij s steklovolokonnymi i titanovymi / Olesova V.N., Klepilina E.S., Balgurina O.S. [i dr.] // Panorama ortopedicheskoj stomatologii. – 2001. – № 3. – S. 22-23.
3. Llojd P.M. Filosofija podgotovki shtiftovogo diametra: obzor literatury/P.M. Llojd, F. Palik//Zhurnal stomatologicheskogo protezirovanija. – 1993. – S.32-35.
4. Buhmjuller K. Sistema shtiftov «Maillefer»/K. Buhmjuller // Dent Art. – 1996. – №4. – S. 39-42.
5. Borovskij E.V. Vnutrikanal'nye shtifty podgotovke zubov k restavracii koronkovoju chasti. / EST" V. Borovskij, I.I. Popova // Klinicheskaja stomatologija. – 2000. – № 2. – S. 32-35.
6. Milot P. Svjaz' pereloma kornja jendodonticheski lechenogo zuba s vyborom shtifta i konstrukciej koronki/ P. Milot, R. Shel'donshtain // Zhurnal stomatologicheskogo protezirovanija – 1992. – S.428-434.